

Subaltern Voices in Amitav Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines* and *The Hungry Tide*.

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ABSTRACT

*The origin of the present research is rooted in the life of Subaltern characters through the different perspectives. The present study describes the concept of subaltern including different statuses like social ,cultural, political and economic point of view. Amitav Ghosh's portrayal of subaltern concepts reflected in novels *The Shadow Lines* and *The Hungry Tide*. The various problems like alienation, migration and existential issues in the life of unprivileged class of the society are included in the term "Subaltern".*

Keywords: Post Colonialism, subaltern ,subaltern theory, Decolonization.

1.INTRODUCTION :

Post Colonialism is an intellectual direction that is subsisted since around the middle of the 20th century. It evolved from and mainly refers to the time after colonialism. Post colonial direction was created as colonial countries became independent.Now- a-days, aspects of post colonialism can be found not only in sciences concerning history, literature and politics, but also in approach to culture and identity of both the countries that were colonized and the former colonial powers. However, post colonialism can take the colonial time as well as the time after colonialism into consideration.

2.OBJECTIVES:

- To study subaltern characters in the selected novels of Amitav Ghosh.
- To study the subaltern reflecting in Indian scenario.
- To study the different problems regarding workers and women social status.

3.REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Post -colonial writings are attempts, at reviving the ethnic cultures, traditions beliefs and languages. The post-colonial literature inculcates pride in one's own ancient culture and traditions and abounds in patriotic feelings. Post colonialism aims at developing the national identity in the wake of colonial rule and deals with the colonized people's response to the colonial legacy by writing back to the center. Post colonial criticism emerged as a distinct category only in the 1990s. One significant effect of post-colonial criticism is to further undermine the universalist claims once made on behalf of literature by liberal humanist critics. If we claim that great literature has a timeless and universal significance, thereby demote or disregard cultural, social, regional, national differences in experience and outlook, preferring instead to judge all literature by a single, supposedly ' universal 'standard.

Characteristically, post-colonial writers evoke or create a pre -colonial version of their own nation, rejecting the modern and the contemporary, which is tainted with the colonial status of their criticism-an awareness of representation of the non- European as exotic or the Immoral 'other'. The emphasis on identity (doubted, hybrid)is a third characteristic of the post-colonial approach, while the stress on 'cross-cultural' interactions is the fourth characteristic of post-colonial criticism. The term 'decolonization' seems to be of particular importance while talking about post- colonialism. In this case it means an intellectual process that persistently transverse the

independence of former colonial countries into people's mind. The basic idea of this process is the deconstruction of old-fashioned perceptions and attitudes of power and operation that they adopted during the time of colonialism. Aspect of post colonialism is the rather violent like, unbuffered contact or clash of cultures as an inevitable result of former colonial times; the relationship of the colonial power to the colonized country, its population and culture and vice-versa seems extremely ambiguous and contradictory. Language is the intellectual means by which post-colonial communication and reflection takes place. This is particularly important as the most colonial powers tried to integrate their language, the major aspect of their civilized culture in foreign societies. A lot of Indian books that can be attached to the era of post colonialism, for instance, are written in English.

Amitav Ghosh occupies a different place in Indian English fiction. He acclaimed as a novelist and a journalist has won the Padmashree, one of India's highest honours, in 2007, was also recipient of Jnanpith Award in 2018. Amitav Ghosh has always kept his audience engrossed, presenting a new paradigm of novel writing remained the focal center of academic discussion extent of a new generation of Indian English writers being earmarked after him as the "Ghosh Generation". Ghosh's fictional world is a curious blend of scholarship, history philosophy and literature suffused with a profound and all-pervading humanism rendered in unique unpretentious style characteristic of the Indian tradition. Ghosh also evinces a liming for the fluid narrative that juxtaposes events in time and space in a way that reflects the contemporary dislocated self. *The Circle of Reason*(1986), *The Shadow of Lines*(1988), *In an Antique Land*(1992), *The Calcutta Chromosome* (1996), *The Glass Palace* (2000), *The Hungry Tide* (2004), *Sea of Poppies*(2001) are the major works of Amitav Ghosh.

The Italian Marxist theorist Antonio Gramsci was firstly coined the word "Subaltern" which term used to denote the group of people who were socially marginalized on basis of their race, religion, gender, colour and ethnicity and are utmost the acknowledged political structure. He first employed the term "Subaltern" in his article "Notes on Italian History" which became later on as part of his Prison Notebooks. He applied the term to delineate the unorganized sections of the people who generally required to be politicized in the concern of the artisan's revolution. The members include in the category of "Subaltern" are women, children, colonial subjects, the poor illiterate, the proletariat and ethnic minority.

Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak abstruse solitude for the functions by which post-colonial studies self-contradictory hold on the substance of political predominance, economic misuse and cultural expunction by exercising the similar system which described in her work "Can the Subaltern speak?". She is dubious about the intention of the post-colonial critic who is inadvertently partaking in the errand of imperialism.

The gist of the subaltern studies significantly focuses on the systems like gender, class, race and caste. The radical identity of a person elevated in the colonial context influences which class of the society speaks of the individual would be appended to. Frantz Fanon opinions of the postcolonial circumstances where the subaltern people are commemorated by their class and marginality.

In Amitav Ghosh's novel *The Shadow Lines* where he inquires the construct of boundaries and the countries by ungrounding the progressive history of transnational flux and migration that began many centuries ago. The anxiety recounted to place and identity is the cardinal dimension of post-colonial literature. In this novel the character of Ila represents the exigency of Identity. Kamala Visweswaran views that Ila descends under the class of "women as Subaltern" and not under the category that of "Subaltern women". On the ground of racial identity Ila belongs to the category of subaltern. She confronts humiliation at her young age who is the victim of racist discrimination.

The female characters like Ila, Thamma and May have seldom been employed by Ghosh to render voice to female subjectivity. They rather articulate the dominant topic of nationalism, Independence and universalism and endure the impediment of the patriarchal society.

The Hungry Tide (2004) as the name suggests is a fascinating novel by Amitav Ghosh in which he narrates the life of the people in the Sundarban twisted and curled by the tide. The meeting of Kanai, Piya and Fokir is beautifully illustrated. Fokir is an illiterate fisherman. Kusum and her son Fokir are the real victims of ejection from the island of Morchjhapi. The settlers in this land are mostly refugees from Bangladesh. People like Kusum, Fokir and Moyna represent the refugees from Bangladesh. For the settlers of this island, life is very risky. Unrest, expulsion and the attacks by tigers are the main problems faced by the settlers. The unpredictable rise of the tidal floods cause destruction in the land. The islands have suffered lots of problems like famine, poverty, catastrophes and failed dreams. Death is the other inevitable reality. In spite of these difficulties people like Kusum dreams even while on exile in Bihar "she had a dream of returning to this place once more this richfield us the strumming tides"(hungry tide, 21).

On the larger part of the narrative, many events happened that include Kanai's reading through Nirmal's journal in which Nirmal has penned his severe love for Bangladeshi refugees who were trying to establish their own settlement in a small uninhabited island of Sundarban called Morchjhapi. Nirmal's love for these refugees is

triggered partly by the socialist ideologies of his youth and partly by the inspiring life of a girl named Kusum once Neelima had given shelter in her trust premises. Nirmal's commentaries focuses on the refugees flight and concentrates on his Utopian idealisms and his love or admiration for Kusum that clash with his wife's pragmatism. Thamma, Ila and author's unnamed mother and May in *The Shadow Lines* are well-educated women belongs to the upper class life of a society unlike Kusum in the *Hungry tide*. Kusum, Fokir's mother is a part of the Morchjhapi revolt and dies in the course of its repression. Ghosh throws light on the reality that money and education fail to spare the women from being considered as a subaltern.

4.METHODOLOGY:

It will be a qualitative analysis including close reading, interpreting and contrasting the primary sources chosen for the study. The selected novels have been analyzed on the perspective of subaltern and its various angles.

5.CONCLUSION :

Amitav Ghosh has succeeded to prove the measurable social, economic, political condition of Indian subaltern people. Ghosh has rightly pointed out the fact that the upper class society repress the significance of poor people in the progress of a nation. The main aim of the researcher is to focus on the exploitation of the people under the category of subaltern in Indian context through the select novels of Amitav Ghosh.

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